

Supplementary Information

DUET-Knockoffs: FDR-Controlled Joint Feature Selection from Dual Microbiome Data

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Supplementary Notes

Supplementary Note 1: Scheme of the bias factor

We assumed that the 1,056 taxa constitute the complete set of underlying taxa in the community and generated platform-specific bias factors $\gamma_{1,j}$ and $\gamma_{2,j}$ for taxon j in the 16S and SMS experiments, respectively. For each platform $k \in \{1, 2\}$ and taxon j , we first drew a baseline log-bias $b_{k,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1^2)$ and set

$$\gamma_{k,j} = \exp\{b_{k,j}\}. \tag{S1}$$

To mimic platform-specific dropout, we then overwrote the baseline values $b_{k,j}$ for selected taxa j . We chose one set of five associated taxa in 16S and another disjoint set of five associated taxa in SMS and set $b_{k,j} = -5$ for these taxa, so that the corresponding $\gamma_{k,j} \approx 0$ and the taxa are effectively absent in that data source. In addition, for each platform we randomly sampled 20% of the null taxa (excluding the most abundant taxon) and again set $b_{k,j} = -5$, thereby introducing systematic experimental distortions that differ between sequencing platforms. Finally, to ensure the existence of at least one stable, well-measured reference-like taxon, we set the baseline value to zero for the most abundant taxon j^* , so that its bias factor is $\gamma_{k,j^*} = 1$ for both platforms. For all remaining taxa not included in the dropout or reference sets, the bias factors $\gamma_{k,j}$ are given by $\exp b_{k,j}$ with $b_{k,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1^2)$ as shown in (S1).

Supplementary Note 2: Implementation details for benchmark methods

The benchmark methods LOCOM [1] and ANCOMBC2 [2] were originally proposed for single-platform microbiome data. Following Yue et al. [3], we extend them to the paired 16S–shotgun setting using two ad hoc integrative strategies: a count-level pooling approach (Com-count) and a p -value-level combination approach (Com-p).

Com-count (LOCOM-Com-count and ANCOMBC2-Com-count). In Com-count, the 16S and shotgun count matrices are first pooled to form a single “augmented” count table. Rows and columns are defined by the union of samples and taxa across the two platforms. For each sample–taxon cell, counts from the two sources are summed when both are observed, copied when only one platform has data, and set to zero when neither platform observes the taxon. LOCOM or ANCOMBC2 is then applied to this pooled table as if it were a single dataset. This construction allows taxa measured in either platform to contribute, but it has two important drawbacks: (i) because shotgun sequencing often has much higher library sizes than 16S, the pooled counts tend to be dominated by the shotgun component, and the resulting test statistics largely reflect the shotgun signal; and (ii) artificially filling zeros for taxa or samples present only in one platform can create pseudo-absence patterns, potentially inducing spurious associations in the pooled matrix [3]. We refer to these extensions as LOCOM-Com-count and ANCOMBC2-Com-count.

Com-p (LOCOM-Com-p). Com-p integrates information at the p -value level and is implemented only for LOCOM (since ANCOMBC2-Com-p showed consistently inflated FDR in our preliminary evaluations and is therefore not included as a benchmark). For each taxon j observed in both the 16S and shotgun datasets, we first fit LOCOM separately to the two count tables, adjusting for the same covariates, and obtain platform-specific p -values $p_{1,j}$ and $p_{2,j}$. These two

p -values are then combined using the Cauchy combination test [4] with equal weights. Specifically, we define the Cauchy statistic

$$T_j = \frac{1}{2} [\tan\{(0.5 - p_{1,j})\pi\} + \tan\{(0.5 - p_{2,j})\pi\}]. \quad (\text{S2})$$

Under general dependence structures between $p_{1,j}$ and $p_{2,j}$, the right tail of T_j is well approximated by that of a standard Cauchy distribution [4]. The combined p -value for taxon j is therefore

$$p_j^{\text{comb}} = \Pr(W_0 > T_j), \quad W_0 \sim \text{Cauchy}(0, 1), \quad (\text{S3})$$

which is the upper-tail probability of the standard Cauchy distribution.

For taxa observed in only one of the two datasets (either 16S or shotgun), no cross-source aggregation is possible; in these cases, we retain the single LOCOM p -value from the observed platform as p_j^{single} . Finally, all taxon-specific p -values, including the Cauchy-combined p_j^{comb} for shared taxa and the single-platform p_j^{single} for taxa present in only one source, are jointly adjusted using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure [5] to control the false discovery rate. We refer to this extension as LOCOM-Com-p.

Supplementary Note 3: Sensitivity analyses for dense signals and unbalanced group sizes

In the main simulations, we focused on balanced case–control designs (50 cases and 50 controls) with a low to moderate proportion of outcome-associated taxa (prop., DA \in 0.05, 0.10, 0.15). To assess the robustness of these findings, we carried out two additional sets of sensitivity analyses based on the Zhu template dataset, summarized in Supplementary Figures S1 and S2. In all panels, solid lines represent empirical power and dashed lines represent empirical FDR, evaluated at a nominal FDR level of 0.2.

Large proportions of outcome-associated taxa. First, we examined scenarios where the vast majority of taxa are truly associated with the outcome by setting prop. DA \in {0.5, 0.75} while keeping the group sizes balanced at (50, 50) and varying the Dirichlet concentration parameter $c \in$ { 10^4 , 10^5 , 10^6 } (Supplementary Fig. S1). These dense-signal regimes are particularly challenging for FDR control.

In terms of FDR, DUET-knockoff remains conservative across all effect sizes and concentration levels, with empirical FDR close to zero even when more than half of the taxa are truly associated. By contrast, all competing methods exhibit substantial FDR inflation in at least some settings. In particular, ANCOMBC2-Com-count shows severe and persistent inflation, while Com2seq and the LOCOM-based combined methods (LOCOM-Com-p and LOCOM-Com-count) fluctuate between moderate inflation and underpowered behavior as c and the effect size vary. Regarding power, DUET-knockoff consistently achieves high power across all dense-signal scenarios, whereas the competing methods either sacrifice power to keep FDR moderate or gain power only at the cost of uncontrolled FDR. These results highlight that DUET-knockoff is the only procedure that simultaneously maintains stringent FDR control and strong power when most taxa are truly differentially abundant.

Unbalanced case–control designs. Second, we investigated unbalanced group sizes while keeping the proportion of outcome-associated taxa fixed at prop. DA = 0.15 and again varying $c \in$ { 10^4 , 10^5 , 10^6 } (Supplementary Fig. S2). We considered two unbalanced designs: $(n_{\text{case}}, n_{\text{control}}) =$ (20, 30) and (40, 60), in contrast to the balanced (50, 50) design in the main text.

Across all unbalanced settings and concentration levels, DUET-knockoff continues to show excellent FDR control, with empirical FDR well below the nominal 0.2 level. Com2seq and the LOCOM-based integrative methods generally keep FDR near the nominal level but display occasional inflation in the most unbalanced and small-sample scenarios, whereas ANCOMBC2-Comcount again exhibits noticeable FDR inflation. In terms of power, DUET-knockoff clearly dominates all competitors, especially in the more unbalanced and lower-sample-size design (20, 30), where it substantially outperforms Com2seq and the LOCOM-based methods across almost all effect sizes. When the group sizes increase to (40, 60), all integrative approaches gain power, but DUET-knockoff still maintains a visible advantage, achieving both higher power and lower empirical FDR than the alternatives.

Overall, these sensitivity analyses confirm that the superior performance of DUET-knockoff is not restricted to the balanced, moderate-sparsity settings emphasized in the main text. Even under dense signals and markedly unbalanced group sizes, DUET-knockoff remains the only method that consistently controls the FDR while retaining high power, reinforcing its robustness for a wide range of realistic study designs.

Supplementary Tables

Table 1. Summary of detected differentially abundant genera in the real data analysis[6, 7].

Dataset	Method	<i>N</i>	Detected genera
ORIGIN overlapping dataset	DUET-knockoff	98	Neisseria, Haemophilus, Prevotella, Veillonella, Lautropia, Megasphaera, Atopobium, Bulleidia, Mogibacterium, Selenomonas
	ANCOMBC2-Com-count	98	Geobacillus, Alloscardovia
Dietary overlapping dataset	DUET-knockoff	195	92
	Com2seq	195	70
	LOCOM-Com-count	195	33
	LOCOM-16s	195	22
	LOCOM-shotgun	195	37

NOTE: *N* denotes the number of genera that passed the filter-cutoff and were included in the analysis.

Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1: Empirical power (solid lines) and FDR (dashed lines) for DUET-knockoff and competing methods at a nominal FDR level of 0.2. Results are shown for template dataset (Zhu) with $\text{prop.DA} \in \{0.5, 0.75\}$ and three different concentration parameters $c \in \{10^4, 10^5, 10^6\}$. Each point is based on 100 simulation replicates.

Fig. S2: Empirical power (solid lines) and FDR (dashed lines) for DUET-knockoff and competing methods at a nominal FDR level of 0.2. Results are shown for template dataset (Zhu) with unbalanced group size $\in \{(20, 30), (40, 60)\}$ and three different concentration parameters $c \in \{10^4, 10^5, 10^6\}$, with the proportion of outcome-associated taxa fixed at $\text{prop. DA} = 0.15$. Each point is based on 100 simulation replicates.

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